

English summary of the Network and its handbook

For the original Network Handbook (in Dutch), see:

Hartsuiker, M., Steinmeier, D., Steeman, M., van Veenendaal, R., Verburg, M., & van Zwol, T. (2025). NDE Netwerk Certificering - Handboek voor leden (0.5). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864522>

Background

The Dutch Digital Heritage Network (Netwerk Digitaal Erfgoed, NDE) is a partnership in the Netherlands that focuses on developing a system of national facilities and services for improving the visibility, usability, and sustainability of digital heritage¹. The network was established in 2014 on the initiative of the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science. All digital preservation activities in the Netherlands have since been concentrated in the Dutch Digital Heritage Network, creating a single national collaboration platform for all institutions that lends more strength to their activities.

Certification is one of the topics of relevance for the partners in the network, as they organise different archives that hold important digital heritage data for the Netherlands. To support the network partners in learning about and achieving certification, particularly trustworthiness certification, a tool was developed to provide information on the topic. This website, the Signpost Certification (Wegwijzer Certificering)², presents information specifically about CoreTrustSeal as a certification scheme and explains how organisations can approach the certification process in a step by step guide.

This static presentation of information has been appreciated and used in the community for quite some years, but there was an increasing desire for more dynamic interactions around the topic. This has led to the development of the NDE Network Certification (NDE Network Certificering)³ in 2024. A community platform has been created where members of the community can share their experiences and advice, ask questions to each other, and share relevant materials and events. From 2025 onwards, meetings will also be organised to discuss relevant topics, challenges, and solutions with each other.

The Network Certification is an example of CoreTrustSeal community building in a specific country and discipline. Efforts like these could be useful in other contexts as well, which is why the core group of the Network Certification have decided to share some insights into the creation of the Network and its handbook in English, for others to use as inspiration in their own efforts of community building.

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<https://netwerkdigitaalerfgoed.nl/en/#:~:text=The%20Dutch%20Digital%20Heritage%20Network.and%20sustainability%20of%20digital%20heritage>

² <https://wegwijzercertificering.nl/nl.html>

³ <https://kiacommunity.nl/groups/216-nde-network-certificering/welcome> Note this is a Dutch website, but the pages can be translated using integrated tools in your webbrowser

Setting up the NDE Network Certification

The NDE Network Certification was created as a follow-up on the already existing Signpost Certification. This tool already had an expert group associated with it, who made decisions around the website, and were responsible for its promotion and related outreach activities. This group represented different partners from the NDE network, chaired by the organisation hosting the Signpost website: Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)⁴. This group together took on the additional activity of preparing the Network Certification for launch.

The planned timeline for the launch covered approximately nine months, from initial discussions to a soft launch event. In this time, most work went towards the creation of the network handbook, in which the rationale of the network is explained and the agreed upon focus areas and workflows are depicted, and the preparation of the community platform.

The choice of community platform was made in alignment with the already existing community standard of the Knowledge community Information & Archive platform (Kenniscommunity Informatie & Archief, KIA)⁵. This platform allows for the creation of topical groups and is organised as a forum where members can share messages and resources. The functionalities available on the platform matched the functionalities desired for the network, facilitating an easy decision.

The soft launch of the Network Certification was attached to a pre existing event organised in November 2024. This gave the best opportunity to reach a wide audience to invite to explore the community platform and provide feedback. Some months after the soft launch were dedicated to inviting people to the platform and sharing the Network online. This period was built in before any true launch so that the list of community members to invite to the first meeting could already be developed.

⁴ <https://dans.knaw.nl/en/>

⁵ <https://kiacommunity.nl/welcome> Note this website is in Dutch

The Community Handbook

The members' handbook of the Network Certification⁶ was written to introduce the Network and its scope, purposes, and processes. This english summary document will briefly summarise the different sections of the handbook. This can facilitate other community efforts to copy elements of the handbook, or otherwise review and improve on them.

It is important to note that the handbook is a living document, that will update when changes are agreed on in the Network and its processes, or when feedback is received. This english summary document will update alongside this, but this may be delayed at times.

Contents

Preface - This introduces the Network and the Handbook document. It also contains the following disclaimer around the Network and its connection to CoreTrustSeal:

The Network Certification enables organisations that would like to (re)certify their repository to have access to the knowledge required to write, evaluate, and submit their application. The Network Certification does not do this work for them.

The Network Certification is an initiative of the Dutch Digital Heritage Network and is not a stakeholder in the CoreTrustSeal organisation. Members of the Network Certification do participate in CoreTrustSeal as reviewer, board member, or administrative supporter, which is a logical consequence of the nature and goals of the Network. All members of the Network Certification ensure that their work for the Network and for CoreTrustSeal are separate. CoreTrustSeal has systems in place that guarantee no one that has contributed and/or evaluated an application will be its Reviewer or decide on its progress in Board meetings.

Terminology - this section contains a table to clarify some of the terms used in the handbook and in communication within the Network. Given some terms are specific to the Network, or can have multiple definitions, this will help all members of the Network understand what is meant.

Goals - The Network Certification has three main goals: awareness raising, support, and knowledge sharing. These goals are explained in this section, detailing why they are important and how they are built into the design of the Network.

Scope and focus areas - In the Network Certification, priority is put on CoreTrustSeal as the main scope and focus area. This choice is explained in this section. Other certification schemas are mentioned, as well as other tools that can be useful in those focus areas.

⁶ Hartsuiker, M., Steinmeier, D., Steeman, M., van Veenendaal, R., Verburg, M., & van Zwol, T. (2025). NDE Netwerk Certificering - Handboek voor leden. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864522>

Participation - This section depicts who can join the Network and the different roles they can have. Four different categories of user groups have been defined:

Starters - Those considering certification for the first time

Applicants - Those working on their first application, desiring support on the processes, writing, reviewing, etc.

Reapplicants - Those working on their recertification

Reviewers - Those part of the CoreTrustSeal Assembly of Reviewers, or those interested in becoming a member

The section also explains the responsibilities of the core group who carry the Network, and how to become part of that.

Formats and processes - This section depicts some practicalities around communications, promotion/dissemination, and file sharing. Information is shared both for the Network as a whole, as well as for the core group specifically.

Feedback is continuously appreciated, on the original Handbook as well as this English summary of it. We also love to hear if you used this document to inspire your own community set-up.

Feel free to reach out to Maaïke Verburg maaïke.verburg@dans.knaw.nl to get in touch on this topic.